

FLEX4H₂

Flexibility for Hydrogen

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4 years (Jan 23 - Dec 26) | Budget €8.7M

Main impacts

New combustor technology for 100% hydrogen

Re-utilisation of existing infrastructure

Contribution to Net Zero pathway

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 Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
 Confédération suisse
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 Education and Research EAER
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